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Linking Practical and Theoretical Learning to Understand Mechanics of Materials

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper, a practical methodology was adopted to stimulate the students for understanding the mechanics of materials course GENG305 through a practical exercise from our life to explain the principals of the subject by building a structure with a regulated specifications, testing the structure under static load until failure, then repairing the structure and re-applying the load until second stage of failure so the structure would fail under the impact of different types of mechanical stresses. Throughout the exercise, the students were requested to explain the causes of the failure, types of stresses involved and proposed a procedure for the repair, since the whole practice is under evaluation. A constructive discussion was conducted with each team during the assessment to ensure that the students are in the right direction of the analysis. At the end, the students' feedback was collected and analyzed to evaluate the experience of the proposed methodology that showed many positive directions that could be implemented for other engineering courses.

Conference Key Areas: Continuing Engineering Education and

Lifelong Learning, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Mechanics of Materials, learning, practical, failure

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INTRODUCTION

Mechanics of materials is a fundamental topic in the college of engineering especially for the civil, architecture, and mechanical engineering department. At UAE University, this course Mech305 is required for the aforementioned engineering departments. Students enrolled in the mechanics of materials after they finish statics course. The course has three credit hours, which consists of two hours lecture and two hours lab and tutorial per week. Both lecture and the lab must cover the learning outcomes of the course that is described in the course syllabus. In general, the course is considered a difficult to the students [1].

Many attempts have been made to reduce this impression through the development of physical demonstration models or using video for classroom use [2], development of computer programs to help, stimulate and facilitate independent learning by students [3], concept inventory research to uncover the underlying cause of learning difficulty with the content [4]. An integrated approach of a new course linking mechanics, materials science and design were developed entitled 'Mechanics and Materials in Structural Design', that educates students in the total design of structures, where one important aspect of this approach is to develop multimedia-based virtual laboratory modules [5]. This module links the mechanics experiment with the fundamentals of materials science and highlights its usefulness in generating design information. On the other hand, a new pedagogy in teaching Strength of Material is experiment-oriented in teaching different units of the Strength of Material in contrast to the math-oriented approach popularly used in most of the Engineering schools. New experiments emphasize on visually observable mechanical behavior so that students can visually inspect the deformation of members when subjected to different types of loadings [6]. A software package, called MDSolids, presents an alternative to tutorials, worksheets, or basic analysis packages. The software was conceived as a tool to help students solve and understand homework problems typically used in the mechanics of materials course. The software is versatile, graphic, informative, and very easy to use. It had been used at a number of schools around the world, and feedback from users has been uniformly positive and enthusiastic [7]. A learning and teaching approach for the course Mechanics of Materials and Structures to level 3 undergraduate Mechatronics and Mechanical Design Engineering students as well as the various technologies that are used to enhance the learning and teaching of the course [8]. To encourage students to be collaborative learners, the students are given the opportunity to generate questions and answer questions generated by other students. This has been implemented using the open source learning resource Peer Wise. Students can learn by both developing questions and answer questions posted by their peers. As matter of fact, the Materials Science and Engineering department at MIT is large enough to offer its own Mechanics of Materials subject, and this subject naturally seeks to blend the materials and mechanics aspects of the discipline. A series of NSF-sponsored, web-available modules are being prepared to support this approach, along with Java applets and other electronic teaching aids. Roylance et al [8] provided an overview of this effort, emphasizing the teaching of fracture mechanics and microstructural failure mechanisms. Jianwei et al [9], showed that during the teaching of material mechanics, with the core of practical cases can not only retain the original advantages but also overcome its disadvantages at a maximum level. Accordingly, the advantage of this methodology is to carry on. Proofed by practice, that the teaching of material mechanics with a core of practical cases is one kind of very effective teaching

model. Wei [10] developed a short course on the mechanical properties and testing of materials in conservation. The goal is to provide students with a basic understanding of what mechanical properties are, how they are used in engineering practice, and how this can be translated to their conservation practice. The course has been successful due to its simplicity, and its emphasis on proper terminology and practical experience. Kadlowec and Navvab [11] had adopted active strategies that also interest and engage students in the learning process could be used to promote learning in educational settings. In an effort to interest and introduce students to engineering principles through a familiar context of sports, a multidisciplinary team of academic staff and students from two universities and a county college developed a set of hands-on modules. Experimentation in one such module allowed for students to explore mechanics of materials at an introductory level. Muscat [12] used the four-stage Kolb learning cycle was used as a model on which to design the set of laboratory activities. An example of a topic in mechanics of materials is used in this study to assess the students' response in terms of Kolb's proposal for effective learning. The topic selected (combined bending and torsion) is part of the mechanical and civil engineering degree curriculum.

The mechanical engineering students of the UAE University enroll in the mechanics of materials course GENG305 at the third year. During teaching in the course, it has been noticed that usually the students face difficulty in understanding the impact of the stresses on the failure of the structures, especially when most of the course subjects are covered and this observed before the final stage of the course. In order to overcome this weakness and before two weeks of the final exam, a comprehensive project was delivered to the students that cover the essential parts of the course material, axial, bending, direct shear and buckling. The students had to choose a structure from the University campus and find the actual dimensions and then using the mechanics of materials principals to calculate the stresses. Part of the project requirements is to build a model on a small scale to represent the structure under certain conditions for the groups, and then during the assessment session, a load was applied gradually to the structure until it fails. Students should explain the reasons and try to repair it and re-apply the load again. This practice results a constructive discussion to clarify the reasons behind the failure of the structure. A survey was distributed after the session to collect the students' feedback that was analyzed to evaluate the knowledge.

1 THE EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1.1 The approach

A paper coated polystyrene foam board of thickness 5 mm (lightweight, strong, easy to cut, they have excellent processing properties) as shown in Figure 1 was used to build the lab model, where four groups used the same boards to maintain consistency. The students were to be asked to select a frame from the University campus as illustrated in Figure 2. The students allowed selecting part of the structure to build their model from the paperboard, so the whole groups followed the suggested part. A 50 mm paperboard was the limit of the paperboard width, and that no more one layer is used. Besides, a scotch tape with a specific type is the only bonding tool that could be used to connect the pieces of the paperboard. The groups agreed on one model to be built as shown in Figure 3 with the dimensions adopted.

Fig. 1. Paper coated polystyrene foam board

Fig. 2. Steel structure from the university campus

Fig. 3. The structure model

1.2 The applied load

After completing the model that was done by the groups, an incremental downward load of 0.1kg was applied on the left side of the structure and the students are instructed to collect observations. Once, a failure or large deflection occurred, the experiment was stopped. An open discussion was conducted to clarify the reasons as well as the alternates for the repair to overcome the consequences. As long as the structure was maintained and ready for another test, the students continue their job until another failure or large deflection occurred.

1.3 The structural model

The model was built using traditional paper coated polystyrene foam board as shown in Figure 4, where 50 mm is the limited width of the elements that can be used to build the structure. Moreover, no glue was permitted for the bonding purposes neither any sort of adhesive, except using traditional scotch tape. T-section was chosen at the beginning as a proposed structural element for both vertical and horizontal elements, whereas a parallel, two flat elements were fixed with the structure using a pencil to represent the joints. Triangular stiffeners were installed at the bottom of the column, that is similar to the real stiffener as shown in Figure 5, but later it was realized that they were not sufficient to resist the moment at the fixed support, therefore bigger pairs were used to resolve this problem, as depicted in Figure 6. Moreover, the T-section was modified to be H-section at the first applied load due to the instability observed in the structure when first launched the first load step.

Fig. 4. The paperboard structural model

Fig. 5. Real stiffeners

Fig. 6. New stiffeners

1.4 Types of stresses studied

Mainly three types of the stresses are considered in this learning experience:

Axial stress $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$ (1)

Bending stresses $\sigma = \frac{M.y}{I}$ (2)

Shear stress $\tau = \frac{V.Q}{I.b}$ (3)

And the critical buckling load $P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot EI}{L_e^2}$ (4)

The aforementioned formulas are used in conjunction with observations to explain the failure mechanism based on the mechanics of materials concepts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

It has been observed that the columns bracing are subjected to high deformation due to axial compressive load, which caused buckling of the braces, as illustrated in Figure 7. Although an attempt was done to add internal stiffeners to the two braces, still the braces failed eventually under buckling, as shown in Figure 8. The whole students with the theoretical explanation understood the buckling failure.

Fig. 7. Buckling started at the braces

Fig. 8. Structure axial load

With applying more incremental load, and despite of the reinforcement done to the failed braces, the structure subjected to high deformation at the column which cause eventually to the failure of the column at the joint, which was caused by the action of three types of the combined loading, bending moment, shear force and axial load. The section failed at the joint, due to the high stresses as well as to the stress concentration caused by the hole of the bolt. A satisfaction and a happiness atmosphere were prevailed among the students due to the unique experience that they faced. Eventually, a survey was distributed and the feedbacks were collected, as listed in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Students' assessment of the lab

(1=very low, 2=low, 3=good, 4=very good, 5=excellent)

1. How do you evaluate the project idea
2. Do you like doing a project instead of HWs
3. Do you think a project covers multiple subjects is a good idea
4. Did you understand the axial, SF and BM through the project
5. Did you distinguished between the hinge and the fixed edge
6. Did you like the experience of testing the project practically
7. Are you able to understand why it did fail
8. Were you able to fix the damage happened based on your understanding
9. Were you able to build the structure from carton and tape without glue
10. Have you ever analyzed a real structure in your study

	1	2	3	4	5
1. How do you evaluate the project idea	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. Do you like doing a project instead of HWs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. Do you think a project covers multiple subjects is a good idea	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. Did you understand the axial, SF and BM through the project	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. Did you distinguished between the hinge and the fixed edge	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. Did you like the experience of testing the project practically	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7. Are you able to understand why it did fail	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8. Were you able to fix the damage happened based on your understanding	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9. Were you able to build the structure from carton and tape without glue	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10. Have you ever analyzed a real structure in your study	<input type="checkbox"/>				

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In general, the students to reflect their feedback about the project experience answered the questionnaire given in Table 1. However, the detailed evaluations of the questions are shown in Figure 9. In general, question one has attracted 79% of the students, which is the highest percentage among the whole questions side by side with questions six and nine., that reflects the overall positive feedback of the project as well as it measures their satisfaction in conducting a practical experience in the course. Although this percentage is reduced to 64% in question, two, which gives the impression about their preferable of the project over the homework, but still the results, are encouraging. Around 93% of the students believe that the project covers multiple subjects of the course that is revealed through the very good and the excellent feedback evaluation, which is an important point at this stage. Nevertheless, this satisfaction for question four is decreased to 72% of the majority positive feedback (i.e., very good and excellent) except the good, which is still an outstanding achievement. A 100% of the positive feedback goes to the understanding the difference practically between the hinge and the fixed support, whereas as grasping the failure causes is dominated by 50% of the excellent and 50% of the very good, which means the obviousness of the practical failure in conjunction with the theoretical explanation. Questions 8 and 9 are a mirror of the hands-on skills that the student have gained as well as reflecting their ability to repair the damaged element during the lab, which is shown by 93% for question 8, and 86% for question 9 for both very good and excellent feedback respectively. Whereas, 7% of the students seem to have poor hands-on skills dealing with building things from soft boards. Eventually, it is clear that a little percentage, 7%, have excellent experience in analyzing structures before, and that is opposite to the students with low (i.e., 21%) practical side, but still 71% have a good and a very good knowledge.

Fig. 9. Results of the students' evaluation of the project

4 SUMMARY

The objective of the study is to improve the students' learning by introducing performance oriented active learning elements in the subject area of the mechanics of materials. Therefore, by linking the theoretical and a practical practice as an additional

practice would improve the students' grasp of the course subjects. The advantage of the pedagogical method is to stimulate the students through applying load to the structure until failure, and then they have to explain the reasons behind it. However, it has been observed that the in-class practical test that covers multiple subjects got a positive feedback and satisfaction in general from the students through understanding the types of the stresses and the failure types and causes

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